

AS LONG AS THERE IS MEMORY - NATION PEACE

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Abstract: man-the flower of life. His value, respect, is always worthy of Honor. When it comes to qualities inherent in our people, of course, such qualities as dignity, kindness are mentioned. Ardoring the elderly, putting the respect of those who need support in place blood is a quality that is absorbed in our blood. In particular, it is special to remember those who have passed away, to receive the blessing of St. otakhonu-onakhans.

Keywords: memory lives with historical memory of Man, nation and people. Memory is such a spiritual and spiritual power that it is a great value, a divine power that symbolizes the humanity of a person, connecting him with the past and perspective.

Introduction

A person needs peace and quiet every day. Neither the household nor the country, who have lost their peace, can truly remain calm. Peace-calmness is a guarantee of progress. Man, Nation and people are blessed with a sense of historical memory. Memory – a symbol of yesterday's past, the agitation of ancestors, our national heritage-illuminates our lives as biblical jewels. Dignity elevates a person, gives nobility to his activities, aspirations, purpose-problems. Demonstrating in practice an example of unbending willpower and courage, the comprehensive prosperity of our dear motherland, the memory of the holy memory of the ancestors who gave their lives for today's peaceful and peaceful days, continuing their noble deeds, honoring the elderly who walked among us – the highest criterion of humanity and a lasting value inherent in our tolerant and noble people who live We have long been a peaceful people. It is this idea that we have a great national spiritual heritage, destined for the targibi. Their bar promotes the value of peace, while the war is completely condemned.

It is this noble goal that lies in the moment when we celebrate May 9 as a national holiday in the style of memory and appreciation day. Still, among us are many participants in the war, and behind the front there are hard-working people. It is necessary to remember those who have passed, and to appreciate those who walk in our ranks.

RESEARCH RESULTS

May 9-day of memory and appreciation serves not to forget the sad consequences of World War II, to appreciate peace and quiet life, to live with a sense of loyalty to the motherland, as well as to always be alert and alert, to educate in the spirit of devotion to historical memory. In short, respect for the spirit of ancestors is one of the highest qualities of our people. Memory is a sacred and dear feeling. Remembrance is the appreciation of the loved ones of every person, the remembrance of the people who have passed through this world and the blessing of their Haqq. There is a saying in our people that "he will find the value he appreciates." In fact, when a person is sincere to others and shows respect, he or she gets the same attitude of those around him. El selflessness, which served for the prosperity of the fatherland and the peace of the people, will not be forgotten by those for life, whose good deeds are the cause.

The names are always venerated and their memories are sealed into eternity. There are officially 3 Memorial Days in Uzbekistan, one of which is the " Memorial Day of the victims " of 2001, the Memorial Day of the first president of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov on September 2, 2016, as well as the third, which has been celebrated since 1999 on May 9-the day of Remembrance and appreciation on the day when Germany was defeated in World War The initiative to name this day as such was announced by the first president of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov. In a speech, our first president said, " Why did we declare May 9 as a day of Remembrance and appreciation? By memory, we understand how to remember our ancestors who passed through this phonic world, turn on their lamp and continue their noble deeds. This is a long-standing quality inherent in our people. There is no prospect of a nation that has no memory, has forgotten history, has no value for its ancestors. This fact is proven by the history of personality. Appreciation means to remember our dedicated compatriots who have defended our motherland, the freedom and independence of our people, the free and prosperous life with valor and diligence for centuries, to show them the respect and respect they deserve," Islam Karimov said. Memory and appreciation – from the centuries-old values, great qualities of our people. People who have fought for the peace, tranquility, land and freedom of El-yurt are always in the ardor of our people. To those who showed such an example of Valor and courage, to honor our ancestors who gave their lives on the battlefield, our enlightened mothers who patiently overcame great difficulties, to perpetuate their memory, to take care and pay attention to them, they were enriched with new meaning and meaning in the years of independence. These aspects are more evident in the day of memory and appreciation, which is widely celebrated in our country, in the care and respect given to our dedicated compatriots who defended our native land, the freedom and independence of our people, the free and prosperous life with valor and enthusiasm. In particular, the decree of our honored President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of April 4, 2017 "on the encouragement of participants in the Second World War"and the decision "on measures to prepare and hold a day of memory and appreciation"became another confirmation of the long-standing value inherent in our people to honor our compatriots who fought for our peaceful and peaceful days, While all this is a symbol of great respect expressed to the noble duogos of our dear land, on the other hand it is clear that the unbiased duoi tributes that they constantly make serve to keep our land and our people from various disasters. And when our Prophet Sallam said, "had there not been between you the old men who had been surrounded, the grazing creatures, and the nursing babies, the calamities would have flowed into your heads like a flood." A person who was originally created a mukarram is always worthy of respect. Especially little in how much to honor and honor our luminous fathers, our dear mothers, who are now of old age, by doing many good deeds in umri dovami. The Blessed hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad sallollohu alayhi vasallam also contained many instructions on how to appreciate our elders and place their respect in place. In this regard, to commemorate the memory of thousands of our compatriots who died in World War II, to our ancestors who returned safely from fiery battles, who patiently overcame hard days, did not lose their identity even in hard times, and to pay tribute to our entire compatriots in faith literally became a national value. This circumstance is incomparable in the upbringing of young people in the spirit of land-building, hard work, pride in the best traditions of their ancestors, becoming worthy successors to them.

In one of his lectures, the head of state said: "historical memory means, first of all, understanding the meaning of life, the sense of succession between generations". Preserving memory, caring for memory is our moral duty to ourselves and generations. Memory is our wealth. Remembering yesterday's lessons, people who gave their lives on the way to the future of our people, teaches us to appreciate our present day. Memory is history. It illuminates our lives as biblical jewels – symbolizing yesterday's past, the agitation of ancestors, our national heritage.

RESULTS OF THE DISCUSSION

For Uzbekistan, it is emphasized that it is important for the international community to understand what deep values may 9 reflects.

First of all, on this day, the spirit of more than half a million Uzbeks who died in the most terrible and bloody World War II in the history of mankind is remembered.

Secondly, may 9 is the day of understanding and appreciating the courage of more than 1.5 million of our compatriots who participated in the war, the tolerance of our people, who received about one million families and children who were transferred from the front lines to Uzbekistan.

Thirdly, on this day, in our history before and after the World War, all our ancestors who gave their lives for the peace and prosperity of our motherland are remembered. Those who are alive are respected and respected, and supportive measures are taken. In a word, may 9 is not only the day of the victory over fascism, but to draw conclusions from the great tragedies that our people saw in war and peace, as a day of appreciation of today's peace, a value that is embedded in the consciousness of our society. Therefore, not to over — politicize the date of may 9, not to succumb to defaults, to celebrate with restraint and reliance on the values of our society-the most correct and acceptable way.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that of course, it is also a duty for all of us to remember our ancestors, who lived in the vital World and left many good things of themselves, became camarabasta in the service of the people, and rebelled from the world of the fan. After all, it is our human duty to remember those who have passed away and ask forgiveness for them, to visit their graves and to pray for them.

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